

Maternal and Child Health Amid Environmental and Climate Change Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Climate change presents a significant threat to human health, especially for pregnant women, newborns and children. It is linked to various complications, including gestational diabetes, hypertensive disorders, preterm birth, low birth weight, stillbirth and mental health issues in mothers. Additionally, climate hazards can affect fertility, increase the risk of miscarriage also cause fetal growth delays and developmental impairments. Children are particularly vulnerable to cognitive, motor and growth issues, while exposure to air pollution can lead to respiratory problems. Climate change also promotes the spread of infectious diseases, such as vector-borne diseases, waterborne illnesses like cholera and cardiovascular diseases. Furthermore, it reduces agricultural productivity and causes financial losses, emphasizing the urgent need for effective climate action to safeguard public health.

KEYWORDS: Maternal Health, Child Health, Environment, Climate Change

INTRODUCTION

The environment refers to the living, non-living, material and non-material things surrounding humans. Apart from the soil, water and air, the environment encompasses the social and economic circumstances of human life. Industrialization, urbanization and other human activities causes pollution of the environment that leads to diseases (Park, 2015). The environment greatly affects human health and climate change exacerbates these impacts (Rocque et al., 2021). In India, the effects of climate change are felt in many different sectors (Hussain et al., 2024). It raises the risk of cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses, lowers agricultural output, results in financial losses, disturbs ecosystems and vegetation, and impedes sustainable development. Climate change impacts health through changes in temperature, rainfall, extreme weather, air quality, rising sea levels, and effects on food and water systems (Caminade et al., 2019). They further added that Climate change is regarded as one of the greatest threats to human health by the World Health Organization. The rate of global warming in recent decades is the fastest it has been in the past thousand years. Furthermore, Climate directly influences the

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occurrence of various infectious diseases, including vector-borne diseases (VBDs), waterborne illnesses like cholera and other soil- and food-borne pathogens.

Climate change is a major threat to human health, particularly affecting pregnant women and newborns, who are more vulnerable than other populations (Conway et al., 2024). Also, Climate change impacts health through extreme weather, food system disruptions, disease spread and mental health issues. furthermore, it also weakens social factors like livelihoods, equality and access to healthcare. Vulnerable groups, including women, children and the poor are most affected. Between 2030 and 2050, climate change is expected to lead to about 250,000 extra deaths each year, caused by undernutrition, malaria, diarrhoea, and heat stress (World Health Organization, 2023).

Goal 13 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasizes the need for immediate action to combat climate change and its effects (Campbell et al., 2018). The SDGs are set to be achieved by 2030, aligning with this estimated timeline (Pathak et al., 2024). Addressing climate change is vital for the

success of the SDGs, with targets 13.1, 13.2, and 13.3b focusing on awareness and capacity building (Sami et al., 2016). Furthermore, The Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEFCC) enforces the National Environmental Policy (2006) to manage air, water, waste, and land degradation. Additionally, NITI Aayog, replacing the Planning Commission is responsible for coordinating SDG implementation in India

Review of Literature

1. Beltran et al. (2014) explored the relationship between seasonality, weather, and three key pregnancy outcomes: hypertensive disorders (such as preeclampsia, eclampsia, and gestational hypertension), gestational length, and birth weight. It finds that women who conceive in warmer months and deliver in colder months have a higher risk of preeclampsia and eclampsia. Additionally, shorter gestation periods are observed for births in both winter and summer.
2. Dalugoda et al. (2022) explored how elevated temperatures during pregnancy are linked to adverse outcomes, including preterm birth, low birth weight, and gestational diabetes, while under-researched outcomes like congenital anomalies and neonatal mortality warrant further investigation. It emphasizes the harmful effects of heat on pregnant women, foetuses, and newborns, underscoring the urgent need for public health interventions to reduce heat-related risks and improve maternal and child health.
3. Eberle and Stichling (2022) talked about Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is a widespread pregnancy complication, with environmental factors such as air pollution, temperature, and chemicals playing a potential role in its development and influencing maternal and offspring health through fetal programming. A systematic review of studies published up to March 2021 examined the links between GDM or glycemic outcomes and environmental factors, including climate conditions, pollutants, and metals. Out of 91 studies, strong associations were identified between GDM and factors such as air pollution, temperature, seasonality, POPs, phthalates, cadmium, and arsenic, while results for phenols were inconsistent. Adverse glycemic outcomes were also strongly connected to these environmental influences. Environmental factors significantly contribute to GDM and glycemic health risks, emphasizing the need for further research to guide prevention and management efforts.
4. Tung et al. (2022) discussed the association between reproduction seasons and postpartum depression, a relationship with unclear implications for mental health. A comprehensive review of PubMed, Cochrane Library, and EMBASE databases identified relevant studies. Information on study design, sample size, seasonal definitions, outcome measures and conclusions were collected. Screening was conducted by two independent authors using PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Out of five studies involving 103,986 participants, the meta-analysis revealed a lower risk of postpartum depression for women who gave birth in spring, summer or autumn compared to winter. Women delivering in non-winter seasons are less likely to experience postpartum depression. These findings can support planning and preventive measures to promote postpartum mental health.
5. Dey (2022) discussed that air pollution has been shown to have detrimental effects on children health in recent epidemiological studies. These effects include low birth weight, stillbirth, preterm delivery, growth failure, developmental delays, poor respiratory and cardiovascular health and an increased risk of anaemia.
6. George et al. (2023) in their study investigates how ambient air pollution and socio-environmental factors, like household wealth, housing quality and smoking status, affect respiratory illnesses in children in India. The study emphasizes the strong link between social-environmental factors and health outcomes in young children in India. Focusing on reducing air pollution, particularly during the monsoon season, could greatly improve child health and help lower preventable deaths in under five children.
7. Xu et al. (2012) conducted a thorough literature review to examine the impact of climate change on health of children. Climate change affects health of children by increasing air pollution causing more extreme weather events, intensifying heatwaves, reducing water quality and availability, creating food shortages and increasing exposure to toxic substances. As a result, children face a higher risk of mental health issues, malnutrition, infectious diseases, respiratory problems and allergies. Study findings revealed that effective mitigation, such as cutting carbon emissions and adaptation measures like early warning systems and post-disaster counselling are crucial.
8. Dziubanek et al. (2013) conducted a research study to analyze the level of awareness of families

about environmental risks and their relation with increased health disorders in children of a selected area of the Silesian Province. The rates of developmental disorders, such as physical and psychomotor ones, in children from this region were estimated. A questionnaire was administered through a door-to-door survey of 2,491 residents to survey perceptions of environmental risks. The findings revealed that parents awareness of environmental health risks was insufficient. While most parents acknowledged the significant impact of the outdoor environment on health, fewer than 1% were aware of indoor environmental risks. The study suggests that educating the community to recognize environmental hazards and providing guidance on how to protect their children are key steps in preventing exposure.

9. Etzel and Bhawe (2023) mentioned that climate change is affecting health of children in many ways and the children of India are the most vulnerable. They are suffering from respiratory problems due to air pollution, heat-related illnesses, malnutrition, diseases spread by vectors and contaminated water and mental health issues such as post-traumatic stress disorder due to climate-induced disasters. There is a need for pediatricians to increase awareness and educate parents about preventive measures. Climate change should be recognized as a child health emergency.

Impacts on Maternal and child Health

1. **Physical health:** Boyles et al. (2021) Environmental stressors have been linked with several short-term maternal health concerns, such as hypertensive disorders during pregnancy, fibroids and infertility. It is also associated with a higher chance of breast cancer.
2. **Mental Health:** World Health Organization (2023) There is a range of maternal and neonatal health impacts of climate hazards like gestational diabetes, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, preterm birth, low birth weight and stillbirth. climate hazards can also have impacts on mental health, both during and after pregnancy. Another research study of Lawrance et al. (2022) showed that climate change has negative impact on mental health of people.
3. **Other impacts:** Tomar et al. (2024) in their research study mentioned that air pollution and heavy metal contamination can harm pregnancy outcomes, particularly in women with existing health conditions. These effects include fetal growth delays, low birth weight, preterm birth, developmental impairments, reduced fertility, and

miscarriage. Exposure to pollutants like lead and mercury can also cause cognitive, motor, and growth issues in children.

Conclusion

The WHO warns that climate change poses significant risks to human health, particularly for pregnant women and newborns. Climate hazards can lead to complications such as gestational diabetes, hypertensive disorders, preterm birth, low birth weight, stillbirth, and mental health issues for mothers. It also affects fertility, increases the risk of miscarriage, and can cause fetal growth delays and developmental impairments. Children may face cognitive, motor, and growth challenges, while exposure to air pollution can lead to respiratory problems. Additionally, climate change increases the spread of infectious diseases, including vector-borne diseases, waterborne illnesses like cholera, and cardiovascular conditions. It also reduces agricultural productivity and causes financial losses.

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